

ON THE USE OF SCIENCE-FICTION GENRE BY H.G. WELLS

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The science fiction genre is considered by many critics and authors to have originated in the 19th century. Herbert George Wells, who played an important role in English prose in this century, is considered by many to be the creator and father of the science fiction genre. In the article, the works of Herbert George Wells in the science-fiction genre were studied and analyzed. His works, which played an important role in his being called the father of this genre, were examined. The history and plot of such works as "Time Machine" and "Invisible Man", which became a source of ideas for future science fiction works, were studied. The topics that George Wells touches on in parallel when using the science-fiction genre - social, political, industrial, etc. allusions - highlighted.

Keywords: science-fiction, Wells, utopia, dystopia, evolutionary theory, time machine, invisibility, futurism.

Introduction

The 19th century, the science fiction genre was widely used, especially in English prose. Various writers applied to this genre and wrote works. The article covers the works of one of these writers, Herbert George Wells. As a result of Wells' scientific knowledge and creative thinking, unforgettable works were created, and his influence was deeply felt in the following centuries. As a result of his ideas, new ideas were created in the science fiction genre, and these ideas were used by different authors for centuries. Wells' works find their embodiment in modern times.

H.G. Wells and his creative work

Herbert George Wells was born in England in 1866. Wells, who lived in the 19th and 20th centuries, wrote unforgettable works. Wells, who tried almost all genres of literature, is remembered as the father of the science-fiction genre. Of course, Wells having created great works in the science-fiction genre with one branch of science, had enough scientific knowledge. He used his creativity along with this knowledge and broad outlook. Also, the time he lived in had a great influence on his creativity. Thus, the changes in industry and transportation as a result of the use of steam power in the 19th century show their traces in Wells' works.

"The Time Machine"

"The Time Machine" written by Wells one of the great examples of the science fiction genre, was published in 1895. It talks about the scientist who invented the time machine, his attempts to travel and the experiences he had during these trips. In the following centuries, the concept of the time machine would become very popular and become a beloved sub-genre in both literature and television. All of them take the source from this novel.

In addition to length, breadth, and depth, Wells considers continuity in this work. The unit that measures this is time. Thus, Wells notes that the three dimensions known to us are related to the present and adds that the fourth dimension, time, connects the past and the future.

The main character of the work is a traveler. If other travelers travel in places, the hero of this work is a time traveler and travels in time. He claims that time is a dimension of space and describes his thinking as follows: "We are always moving away from the moment we are in. Our immaterial, dimensionless mental

existence passes through the dimension of time from birth to death at an unchanging speed". He means that just as a person can move forward and backward in a space, this also exists in time. Even such an issue has been raised by the readers about the traveler who has traveled all the time in one day, that why does he not return to the moment he started after returning from the journey,? According to Parrinder, who is known for his studies of Wells, as time moves forward, the time machine approaches its end, just as man approaches his death. Wells' goal in this work is to go beyond death.

As in other works of the science-fiction genre by Wells, this work also contains political allusions, the author's criticism of his own time. As a result of these, the work embraces dystopia and utopia. So the simultaneous existence of these two concepts in the work, is sometimes called "Dystopia within Utopia" by critics.

In the novel, the journey takes place like this: A time traveler chooses a date he wants to travel to. After arriving there, the first thing that he notices is a large building that looks like a sphinx. And people are very different from what they were in his time. About 1 meter 20 cm tall, with shiny faces and the same hairstyles, these human beings speak a cheerful, flowing language, and wear clothes that look like robes. They seem very simple to the traveler. He had planned to go to the future and meet an advanced human race, but the situation he encountered disappoints him. Wells describes his feelings at the time as follows:

"All of a sudden, a question came to my mind: were these beings unintelligent? You cannot imagine how this idea affected me. It is known, I always predicted that in the year 802, 701 people will be far ahead of us in science, art and everything else. Suddenly, one of them asked a question of the type that a five-year-old child would: I came from the sun in a thunderbolt?! ... Instead of blood, disappointment flowed into my brain. For a moment I thought that there was no point in building a time machine."

As a result of the traveler's facing reality and this inner fear, the situation he previously called utopia turns into dystopia for him. But Wells actually shows utopia with these events. There is no ownership of property among men; no fences; they don't work; they do not care about the future for their children. There are also Darwinist factors in this work. A balance has emerged in nature; No harmful plants or animals are

present. Medicine has reached its goal. There is no class or economic competition. All the issues that are against the development of people have disappeared.

Wells' time traveler decides to use the time machine again because he perceives this situation as a dystopia but he comes across a real dystopia. He explores the underground and the dark as he searches for the time machine. The Eloi whom he first saw and knew lived a very safe life in the morning. But at night they slept in one place and in the light. So the traveler is interested and realizes that humanity is not made up of one species; it has become two kinds of animals. These sentient Earthlings are not the sole inheritors of the human race, but the abominable creatures called Morlocks are also the inheritors of all ages.

Morlocks are lemur-like, red-eyed, yellow-haired, fast creatures that can climb like spiders. They go underground with wells and live there. The Morlocks feed on the Eloi. Also their language is different. To explore them, the traveler who goes underground barely survives. Wells compares these two species, which he gave as the heirs of humanity, economically, and considers them as poor and rich.

The traveler then makes several more trips. In the end, it almost comes to the end of the world. At that time, the Sun does not rise or set, the Moon does not appear, the sky is not blue, etc. What the traveler meets does not coincide with what he expected, and this creates disappointment in him.

"The Island of Doctor Moreau"

In 1896, H. G. Wells published his next work in the science-fiction genre: "The Island of Doctor Moreau". This novel is both exemplary and one of the famous works. The work caused a sensation in Europe and America. Experiments conducted on animals reminded the readers of the pain of animals and they figured out that these events happened in real life. As a result of the indicated reaction, the cases of conducting experiments on animals have decreased.

Edward Prendick is one of the characters in the work. Events the novel is first-person narrative, which brings him closer to the reader. Edward experiences a shipwreck and is brought to an island in the middle of the Pacific Ocean. The island is surrounded by Dr. Moreau, who devoted himself to "scientific" experiments on that island, his assistants and strange creatures that are the result of his experiments.

Dr. Moreau is a gifted geneticist who studies evolution. He also experimented with genetics in England and gained notoriety. As a result, he is expelled from the country and finds this island to carry out his experiments. He considers his goal, which is worth all these dangers and sufferings, to be supreme, and for this he puts not only himself, but all humanity in danger. But what does Dr. Moreau do?

Dr. Moreau experiments on animals. But these practices are more frightening and unethical than normal practices. Thus, it causes deformations on animals; tries to humanize them. These deformations do not only occur physically. The animals both look and walk like humans and think like humans as a result of Moreau's changes to their brains. Prendick learns this by acci-

dent, because Moreau himself did not want these experiments to be studied until they were completely successful. But Prendick thinks that he will be the next experiment object. That's why he tries to run away from there. During his time in the forest, he comes across pigs and monkeys that look like humans. As in his other works, Wells criticizes society here. Dr. Moreau's creatures formed a community. According to them, their creator Moreau is considered a god and they are ready to obey him. A herd of monkeys deifies Moreau and even sings for him. Their leader is a large, gray, unknown creature who recites to him a strange litany called the Law, which contains prohibitions against savage behavior and praises for the Moreau.

Not to go on all-fours; that is the Law. Are we not men?

Not to suck up Drink; that is the Law. Are we not men?

Not to eat Fish or Flesh; that is the Law. Are we not men?

Not to claw the Bark of Trees; that is the Law. Are we not men?

Not to chase other Men; that is the Law. Are we not men?

After all this - what he saw, what he experienced, - when Prendick returns to England and he sees people, it seems to him that they are about to turn into animals. He begins to feel strange and uncomfortable around people. As a result, he leaves London and moves to a foreign place; engages in chemistry and astronomy research.

"The Invisible man"

"The Invisible Man" is the next novel of Wells in the science-fiction genre. It was published in 1897. In this work, again, an unusual discovery is mentioned. This time, this discovery is invisibility. He invents invisibility, but cannot control it. The novel has great popularity among readers and critics. It even played an important role in the recognition of Wells as the "father of the science-fiction genre".

Dr. Griffin is a mysterious man. He only goes out at night, does not spend time with others and lives in a hotel. It is not visible under normal conditions, but food passing through his stomach when he eats and footprints in the mud when he walks are visible. Therefore, he wears clothes, hats and scarves, and hides his face with a bandage, so that it is not obvious that he is invisible. When he is at home, he conducts experiments using chemicals.

Griffin devoted himself to research in optics. He discovered a way to change the refractive index of an object to that of air so that the body does not absorb or reflect light. He performs this procedure on himself, and the events do not develop correctly: the attempt to return to the previous state fails. When people learn that he is invisible, they do not trust him and it becomes more difficult for him to communicate with people. This is also reflected in his relationship with the people around him. Griffin, who uses his invisibility to harm people, is eventually defeated. At the same time, this work, which is called horror fiction, has gained immortality with the image of Griffin.

Russian writer Yakov I. Perelman in his book "Physics Can Be Fun" (1962) notes that scientifically, a person who is invisible by Griffin's method must be blind, because the human eye absorbs incoming light and does not let it in completely.

"The War of the Worlds"

In 1898, Wells' next work, "The War of the Worlds", was published. This work, written by H.G. Wells, talks about the Martian invasion of the world. Although there have been many fiction and television works about world invasions, "The War of the Worlds" is one of the first and most famous novels about it. Even when talking about the work on the radio, many listeners thought that the world was really under such an occupation.

An explosion occurs on the surface of Mars and a meteor falls on London. The Martians, emerging from the cylinder-like containers, start killing people. Of course, their weapons are more advanced. Giant war machines with three legs, heat-ray and poisonous black smoke are among their most effective weapons. Then the aliens suddenly start dying. But you see, the Martians are not suitable for this world and are infected with the virus. The rest leave the world, but in doing so they become a constant source of fear. Because it is not clear when their next arrival will be.

Wells again uses political allusions. In the work, he mentions that as a person develops, he also brings his own end. With this, he compares the most developed empire of the 19th century with the developing man. Hiding in a house during the Martian invasion, the character, when he comes out at the end of the period, has some thoughts like this:

"At that moment ... I felt no different than a rabbit who encounters a group of people digging up and destroying its nest when it thinks it is returning to its nest. I was beginning to believe that I was an animal subordinate to the Martians... the terrible empire of mankind was over."

"Tales of Space and Time" and short stories by Wells

In 1899, the collection "Tales of Space and Time" was published. It contains three short stories and two novellas. These are the stories "The Crystal Egg", "The Star" and "A Story of the Stone Age", "The Story of the Days to Come", "The Man Who Could Work Miracles".

"The Crystal Egg"

"The Crystal Egg" is a short story; It was written in 1897. The main character in the story is Mr. Cave. He is a shop owner. Mr. Cave finds an unusual egg. He figures out that it acts as a portal to Mars. The plot bears strange similarities to and sets the stage for War of the Worlds, as the Martians' attempt to observe humanity indicates their readiness for a future invasion.

"The Star"

The next work is the apocalyptic short story "The Star". Astronomers report here that there is instability in the orbit of the planet Neptune. It turns out that an unusually bright object entering the solar system is causing a problem in its gravity. "Collision of planets"

is predicted by astronomers. The collision causes an explosion. As a result, with each passing day, the star appears bigger and people realize that it is getting closer.

Some people take it as the end of the world, others are just interested in the star. Scientists assure people that there will be no danger. But even if this star is millions of years away, it causes the melting of the Earth's ice sheets, thus causing floods. The star's gravity results in massive earthquakes, rising and falling water levels, volcanoes and hurricanes. All the islands are also destroyed. Millions of people die. As everyone waits for the collision, a shadow suddenly appears and blocks the unbearable light and heat from the star. It turns out that the gravitational force of the Earth's satellite has pushed the star away.

"A Story of the Stone Age"

"A Story of the Stone Age", published in 1897, is a short story written by Wells. Events take place in the Stone Age. A caveman called Ugh-lomi and his wife Odena are the heroes of the work. Ugh-lomi kills another tribal leader, Uya. Ugh-lomi is sent into exile, and there he rides a horse, combines stone and wood to make an ax. He shot a bear, a rhinoceros, etc. using the gun. In the end, he says that he considers himself suitable for the position of the head of the tribe.

"The Story of the Days to Come"

"The Story of the Days to Come" is a novella published in 1899. The heroes of the work are two lovers. The events take place in London of the 22nd century. In the work, Wells talks about the process of urbanization, class wars, and the consequences of advances in technology. The future is predicted to be mass urbanization, skyscrapers, moving sidewalks, superhighways, advertising, mass media, psychotherapy, technical developments toward intercontinental airplanes. The lower classes live in underground houses, while the middle and upper classes live in skyscrapers. Air travel and highways are available between cities. Villages were abandoned.

The plot begins with a girl with an inheritance falling in love with a boy from middle-class. A father finds a hypnotist so that his daughter can be with someone suitable. When the girl finds out about this attempt, the couple gets married secretly and flees to the abandoned villages. After some suffering, they finally solve the problems and live a mediocre life.

"The Man Who Could Work Miracles"

"The Man Who Could Work Miracles" is a short story published in 1898. The work, which is considered the first example of modern fiction, begins with George McWhirter Fotheringay's assertion of the impossibility of miracles. Fotheringay orders the oil lamp to be lit. But unexpectedly, what he says comes true. The more he is surprised by the incident, the more his friends do not believe it.

After performing a series of miracles like this, Fotheringay begins to attend church. The cleric Maydig tells him about supernatural events. Fotheringay asks Maydig for advice about what he's going through. After a few small demonstrations, Maydig is motivated and decides to use these abilities for the benefit of others. They walk the streets, heal the sick, improve public af-

fairs. Thus, Maydiq plans to reshape the world. He suggests that Fotheringay stop the motion altogether. Thus, people would not have any obligations for the next day. Fotheringay stops the movement of the Earth. This causes everything on Earth to be ejected from the surface with great force, destroying all of humanity. No matter how hard Fotheringay tries, he can't bring Earth back. He repents and prays that this power given to him will be taken away and the world will return to its former state. Fotheringay suddenly finds himself discussing miracles with his friends and has no memory of the previous events.

The role and the influence of H.G. Wells

Although the signs of the genre, which is called science-fiction today, have existed since ancient times, the creation of the first original independent science-fiction work is attributed to the 19th century. A number of critics consider Mary Shelley's "Frankenstein" to be the first work of science fiction. For some, H.G. Wells' works are the first examples of this genre.

Wells uses scientific-fiction tools to tell didactic ideas on society in their stories. For example, in the "Time Machine" (1895), the technical details of the car are not given in detail, instead, the time traveler is allowed to tell stories criticizing the stratification of the English society. The novels and stories of Wells also include the ideas influenced by Darwin's Evolution theory and Marxism.

Conclusion

The article analyzes the works of H.G. Wells, who is considered the creator of the science fiction genre. It

was determined that there were examples of the science-fiction genre before. However, some critics consider Welles to be the creator or father of science fiction due to his contributions to the genre. Wells used his scientific knowledge to enrich this genre. The images in his works retained their influence in the following centuries. The social issues he emphasized in his works left an impact on the society and his political allusions targeted the shortcomings of the government. The article describes the works in detail. The characteristics of the images in the works were studied and analyzed. In addition, the opinions of various thinkers about Wells' creativity and works are mentioned.

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